

MODERN FORMS OF ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT WORK OF STUDENTS AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *The process of using innovative technologies in higher education institutions is manifested both in the content of subjects and in the methods, tools and forms of teaching.*

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The reforms carried out in today's educational system are aimed at developing independent thinking of students, based on individual educational trajectories, eliminating problems related to creative thinking in students, the formation of practical skills. In higher education institutions, it is planned to proceed in stages to the implementation of these tasks. Today, among the main problems are the low share of independent hours of education in the higher education system, independent education in students, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, lack of formation of entrepreneurial skills, educational process, organizational skills in institutions, and the imposition of techniques and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies does not correspond to modern demand. Therefore, increasing the share of independent educational hours in the higher education system, obtaining independent education in students, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, the formation of entrepreneurial skills, the introduction of techniques and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies in the educational process, the orientation of the educational process to the formation of practical skills, the widespread introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and educational methodological materials In modern conditions, according to all the possibilities of the educational process, it is required to focus on the development of personality, socialization and the upbringing of independent, critical, creative thinking skills in it. It should be ensured that highly qualified specialists will be prepared according to consumer requirements, and the formation of knowledge, skills and qualifications of students in their chosen specialties will be independently trained in knowledge and practical activities. Since it is interpreted as a problem for the development of organizational abilities of students in the process of independent education, it can be cited that the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on Education", approved on September 23, 2020, also defines "independent education is carried out individually and serves the professional, intellectual, spiritual and cultural development of learners In the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures for the further development of the higher education system": "each higher educational institution to establish close ties with the world's leading scientific and educational institutions, to widely introduce advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and educational and methodological materials based on international educational standards to the educational process, to actively attract highly qualified teachers and.."emphasis is placed on importance. Currently, further improvement of the educational process, educational plans and programs of Higher Education on the basis of the widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies and teaching methods, qualitative updating of the master's educational

process and the introduction of modern organizational forms are among the main problems and, based on these procedures, higher education. In the context of today's globalization, it is advisable to use advanced pedagogical technologies and active methods in the educational process, to implement the newly produced technical means, to encourage more students to work independently, to widely use different ways of teaching lessons from advanced experiments. Another aspect is important that it is necessary to ensure the effective organization of the teaching of special subjects so that students studying in the higher education system can develop their inclinations, abilities, knowledge and skills in their chosen profession, to be formed as specialists in their chosen areas. As in any society, the main problem in the development of our republic is the training of qualified specialists who can withstand competition in the conditions of a market economy. Extensive work has been done and is being done in recent years on the training of specialist personnel, improving its quality and efficiency. In particular, special attention is paid to the content of such qualities as independence, creativity, entrepreneurship, activity of the trained specialist personnel. How to perform independent work in educational institutions is carried out by each student himself. In order to achieve success, the student himself must work on himself with patience, without fear of hardships. And this is planned and done by the student himself. Problems, changes in all aspects of society also affect the process of training students at higher educational institutions and make new demands.

Even now, there is a great need for specialists, personnel who have theoretical knowledge and practical skills, are adaptable to changes, are free-minded, can independently solve professional and life problems. At the same time, higher education institutions require from their students a level of comprehensiveness, independent thinking, a person with organizational skills. The fulfillment of such requirements is certainly ensured by teaching them to acquire knowledge throughout their lives. In the context of Active Education, acquired knowledge, acquired skills and competencies are formed in a systematic and logically completed way, allowing them to be used in various production situations. Activating learners allows them to develop their independent learning skills. We can say that the problem of developing organizational abilities of students in the process of independent education as yuechimi is to gradually transfer the educational process in higher education institutions to the kreditmodul system. The concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 showed that by 2030, 85% of all higher education institutions (universities) in the Republic, including the transfer of 33 higher education institutions to the credit - modular system in the 2020/2021 academic year itself. A credit-module system, which is the process of organizing education, is a model of assessment based on a set of Modular Technologies of teaching and a measure of credit. Carrying it in one whole is a lush and complex systemic process. In the principle of credit-module, importance is given to two main issues: ensuring the independent functioning of students; assessment of student knowledge on the basis of rating. Therefore, the credit - module system consists not only in conducting lesson training on the basis of innovative educational technologies, but also in learning independently from the student, in a new way to the education, acquiring the necessary and deep theoretical knowledge based on the demand of the labor market, teaching the formation of practical skills. In short, this system is aimed at the professional development and maturation of the student. It can be said that science is aimed at ensuring the knowledge of the owner throughout his life and the formation of human capital, which can meet the labor market and modern requirements. The introduction of a credit-module system is an important factor in the collaborative work of the

teacher and student. In modular education, the educator organizes, manages, advises, examines the process of mastering the listener. And the student acts independently towards the directed object. The greatest emphasis is also on the Independent Education of students. Higher education institutions in the process of Independent Education, the development of organizational abilities of students is one of the main tasks.

Conclusion

In this regard, we consider it advisable to carry out systematic work on the following areas. First of all, on the basis of the reforms in the educational system implemented today, the teaching process should be organized in such a way as to increase the awareness and activity of those who receive education, in which students consciously and actively occupy scientific knowledge and methods of their application, focusing on creative initiative in them and ensuring independence in educational activities, Secondly, to popularize the work of novice teachers who have achieved success in this area, to develop the work of exchange of experience on the road. Thirdly, today in the era of digital economics, ways to formulate and formalize the information of students regarding independent education on the basis of the requirements of the time. Fourth, to establish the possibility of using foreign experience in the development of organizational abilities of students in the process of Independent Education. Based on the points listed above, it can be said that in the implementation of the independent educational process in higher educational institutions, the establishment of systematic work, the teaching of students to work independently will become the basis for the formation of a new generation of personnel who are creative and socially active, have the skills to be able to independently find their place in socio - political life, Quality communication between a teacher and a student in the process of independent work, students assume the role and importance of a teacher in the process of independent work, management functions, the use of information communicative technologies, mobile technologies to highlight the independent work of students as a modern form - pedagogical problem.

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